

STUDIES ON THE EFFECT OF DIFFERENT FARMING PRACTICES ON SOIL MICROBIAL STATUS AND YIELD OF WHEAT (*Triticum aestivum* L.) IN INCEPTISOLS

Rutuja R. Patil, Ashok C. Jadhav*, Tejaswini Sabale and Abhishek Mohite

Department of Plant Pathology and Agricultural Microbiology,
Mahatma Phule Krishi Vidyapeeth, College of Agriculture, Pune, Maharashtra (India)

jadhavacj@gmail.com

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Abstract

The present investigation on "Studies on the effect of different farming practices on soil microbial status and yield of wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) in Inceptisols" was conducted at the "A" block of Agronomy Farm, College of Agriculture, Pune-5 in Rabi season 2023-24 in Randomized Block Design with five treatments and four replications. The present investigation was conducted with the aim to estimate the periodical population of microorganism in soil and to study soil enzymatic activities under different farming practices. This experiment included farmer's practice treatment, MPKV recommended package of practice treatment, organic farming treatment, natural farming treatment and climate resilient farming treatment. Microbial population of fungi, bacteria, actinomycetes, Azotobacter, PSB and KMB were recorded. Also, alkaline phosphatase, acid phosphatase, urease and dehydrogenase enzyme activity in soil were recorded at 50 per cent flowering and at harvesting of wheat crop.

It was observed that the organic farming found to be most effective in respect to microbial population and enzymatic activity in soil. Followed by climate resilient farming treatment and MPKV recommended package of practice treatment. Climate resilient farming treatment recorded higher grain yield and straw yield. During the investigation, higher microbial population of fungi (24.17×10^5 cfu g⁻¹ soil), bacteria (214.17×10^6 cfu g⁻¹ soil), actinomycetes (35.42×10^4 cfu g⁻¹ soil), Azotobacter (29.42×10^5 cfu g⁻¹ soil), PSB (25.67×10^5 cfu g⁻¹ soil) and KMB (23.33×10^5 cfu g⁻¹ soil) at 50 per cent flowering were recorded in organic farming treatment. Higher enzyme activity of alkaline phosphatase ($12.32 \mu\text{g PNP g}^{-1} \text{hr}^{-1}$), acid phosphatase ($10.00 \mu\text{g PNP g}^{-1} \text{hr}^{-1}$), urease ($26.75 \mu\text{g NH}_4^+ \text{-N g}^{-1} \text{hr}^{-1}$) and dehydrogenase ($14.12 \mu\text{g TPF g}^{-1} \text{soil } 24 \text{ hr}^{-1}$) at 50 per cent flowering were also recorded in organic farming treatment. In respect to yield, higher grain yield (43.16 q ha^{-1}) and straw yield (59.56 q ha^{-1}) recorded in climate resilient farming treatment. The above investigation concluded that organic farming treatment was best with regard to microbial population, enzyme activity in soil and yield of wheat crop.

Keywords: Wheat, biofertilizers, microbial population, organic farming, farming practices, enzymes activity.

Introduction

Wheat, a vital cereal grain from the genus *Triticum*, primarily includes varieties like *Triticum aestivum*. It serves as a staple food globally, classified into hard, soft, and durum types based on protein content and intended uses in products like bread, pastries, and pasta. Nutritionally, wheat is rich in carbohydrates, protein, dietary fibre, and essential vitamins and minerals. While it provides a good energy source, it also has a high glycemic index. Whole wheat flour is particularly noted for its fibre content, which supports digestive health (Iqbal *et al.*).

Organic farming is integral to sustainable agriculture, emphasizing biodiversity and soil health. Techniques such as crop rotation, cover crops, and the use of organic manures are vital for improving soil fertility and preventing pests, making organic wheat production environmentally friendly. Natural farming focuses on utilizing local resources and minimizing external inputs. By combining traditional knowledge with modern techniques, it enhances soil health and biodiversity, promoting sustainable practices that can yield results comparable to conventional methods. Climate-resilient farming enhances food security, especially in regions affected by climate change. New wheat varieties that tolerate drought and heat are being developed, allowing farmers to achieve greater yields with lower environmental impact (McCoy, 2002).

The periodical population of microorganisms in a wheat crop can be estimated by analysing the structure and dynamics of the wheat micro biome during the growing season. The rhizosphere is the soil immediately surrounding the plant roots, harbours a diverse array of microorganisms that interact with the plant. Studies have proved the changes in fungal and bacterial communities related with wheat plants at different developmental stages and under various environmental condition as well as alterations in the soil microbial profiles and increases the rhizosphere's beneficial bacterial species because of wheat cultivation (Chen *et al.*, 2022).

Biofertilizers play a crucial role in sustainable agriculture by enhancing soil health and reducing reliance on synthetic fertilizers. They restore nutrient cycles and improve soil properties, supporting long-term fertility and crop yields. Unlike synthetic fertilizers, biofertilizers do not leave harmful residues and contribute to lower pollution levels. Their application promotes healthier soil and water quality, making them an eco-friendly option for farmers. *Azotobacter*,

phosphate solubilizing bacteria (PSB), and potassium mobilizing bacteria (KMB) are essential for improving nutrient availability in crops. Their combined use in farming practices boosts nitrogen fixation, phosphorus solubilization, and potassium mobilization (Game *et al.*, 2020).

The activity of urease, phosphatase and dehydrogenase enzymes in crop fields is crucial for understanding soil health and fertility. These enzymes are crucial for nutrient cycling and microbial activity, both of which are vital for the growth of plants. Furthermore, these enzymes are critical indicators of soil health and fertility in crop fields. Their activities can be significantly affected by agricultural practices, including the use of fertilizers and the control of soil pH. Understanding these enzyme dynamics can aid in optimizing soil management strategies to improve agricultural yield and sustainability (Symanowicz *et al.*, 2022).

In conclusion, the utilization of a biofertilizer consortium containing *Azotobacter*, PSB and KMB is for improving crop growth, yield and nutrient uptake. Above mentioned synergistic effect leads to better nutrient uptake by crops, which is essential for their growth and productivity. The utilization of this consortium not only enhances crop production but also enriches the soil's residual nutrient levels after harvesting. The current research aims to assess the impact of biofertilizer consortiums containing *Azotobacter*, PSB, and KMB on wheat crop yield and growth. Conducted during the Rabi season 2023-24 at the Agronomy Farm in Pune, this study seeks to understand the effects of different farming practices on soil microbial status.

Material And Methods

The current study was carried out during Rabi season of 2023-24 under field condition at Agronomy farm, College of Agriculture, Pune, Maharashtra to study the microbial populations and enzymatic activities in soil under various farming practices. The experimental field topography was uniform and levelled. The soil of experimental sites was medium black in colour and well drained, with a uniform depth up to 90 cm. To determine the physical, chemical and biological composition of the soil of the experimental site, samples were taken from 0 to 30 cm depth at 5 randomly selected places in a zig-zag pattern throughout the experimental area and a composite sample was prepared and analyzed.

Treatment details

The wheat variety *Phule Samadhan* was grown as test crop. The field experiment comprised following treatments.

Farmer's practice (T1):

Application of chemical fertilizers 45:115:00 kg ha⁻¹ N, P₂O₅ and K₂O.

MPKV recommended package of practice (T2):

Seed treatment with thiram @ 3g kg⁻¹ seed and with thiamethoxam 30 per cent FS 7.5 ml 10 kg⁻¹ seeds followed by seed treatment with MPKV consortium of *Azotobacter*, PSB and KMB @25 ml kg⁻¹ seed.

Organic farming (T3):

Seed treatment with MPKV consortium of *Azotobacter*, PSB and KMB @25 ml kg⁻¹ seed. Primary tillage operations. Application of FYM @ 10 t ha⁻¹ and vermicompost @8 t ha⁻¹.

Natural farming (T4):

Zero tillage operations. Soil application of Ghanjeevamritha @ 2000 kg ha⁻¹ during field preparation. Mixed cropping with broadcasting of Lucerne @ 12 kg ha⁻¹. Seed treatment of Beejamrit. Mulching of soybean crop residues. Application of Jeevamritha @ 500 L ha⁻¹ along with irrigation water after sowing. Then application of Jeevamritha @ 500 L ha⁻¹ along with irrigation water twice in month.

$$\text{No. of bacteria/fungi/actinomycetes per g soil} = \frac{\text{Average plate count} \times \text{Dilution factor}}{\text{Oven dry weight of 1g soil sample}}$$

Assay of soil enzyme:

The activities of soil enzymes viz., urease dehydrogenase, acid and alkaline phosphatase were measured by using standard methods.

Sr. no.	Enzyme	Method	Reference
1.	Dehydrogenase	Spectrophotometry	Casida <i>et al.</i> (1964)
2.	Acid Phosphatase	Spectrophotometry	Evazi and Tabatabai (1977)
3.	Alkaline Phosphatase	Spectrophotometry	Evazi and Tabatabai (1977)
4.	Urease	Titrimetry	Tabatabai and Bremmer (1972)

Observations Recorded

The observations on microbial population and soil enzyme activity were recorded at initial (before sowing), at 50 per cent flowering and at harvest stages of wheat crop.

results And Discussion

Effect of different farming practices on microbial population in soil at 50 per cent flowering and at harvest of wheat crop.

The data on microbial population in soil at 50 per cent flowering and at harvest stage in wheat as influenced by different treatments are presented in Table 1.

The microbial population of fungi was significantly influenced in organic farming treatment (T₃). It recorded higher fungal population (24.17, 17.42 x 10⁵ cfu g⁻¹ soil) at 50 per cent flowering and at harvest, respectively. It was found statistically at par with the treatment T₅ (climate resilient farming) and T₂ (MPKV recommended package of practices) for fungal population. While lower fungal population was recorded in farmer's practice treatment (T₁). The organic farming treatment recorded higher microbial population of bacteria (214.17 and 208.92 x 10⁶ cfu g⁻¹ soil) at 50 per cent flowering and at harvest respectively. Least microbial count of bacteria was recorded in farmer's practice treatment (T₁). Treatment T₃ *i.e.*, organic farming recorded maximum microbial count of actinomycetes (35.42 x 10⁴ cfu g⁻¹ soil) at 50 per cent flowering and (30.08 x 10⁴ cfu g⁻¹ soil) at harvest. While minimum microbial count of actinomycetes was recorded in farmer's practice treatment (T₁). Among all the treatments, the higher microbial population of *Azotobacter* (29.42 and 22.92 x 10⁵ cfu g⁻¹ soil) was noticed in organic farming treatment at 50 per cent flowering and at harvest respectively and was found statistically at par with the treatment T₅ (Climate resilient farming) and T₂ (MPKV recommended package of practices). While the lowest *Azotobacter* population was noticed in farmer's practice treatment (T₁). The higher count of PSB (25.67 and 19.25 x 10⁵ cfu g⁻¹ soil) were recorded in organic farming treatment (T₃) at 50 per cent flowering and at harvest respectively. Followed by treatment T₅ (climate resilient farming) and T₂ (MPKV recommended package of practices). Farmer's practice treatment (T₁) recorded lowest PSB population. The KMB population was significantly influenced in organic farming. It had higher KMB

Climate resilient farming (T5):

Primary tillage followed by zero tillage. Seed treatment with Thiram @ 3g kg⁻¹ seed followed by seed treatment with MPKV consortium of *Azotobacter*, PSB and KMB @25 ml kg⁻¹ seed. Sowing of wheat on ridges and furrows. Mulching of soybean straw and leaf litter. In situ decomposition of leaf litter and straw after harvest of wheat followed by green manuring of dhaincha.

Isolation of microorganisms

The total number of fungi, bacteria, actinomycetes, *Azotobacter*, PSB and KMB from soil were estimated before sowing, at 50% flowering and at the time of harvesting by serial dilution pour plate method. Counted the number of bacteria, fungi, actinomycetes, *Azotobacter*, PSB and KMB colonies in each plate and calculated the average number of bacteria, fungi, actinomycetes, *Azotobacter*, PSB and KMB per gram of soil.

The number of bacteria, fungi, actinomycetes, *Azotobacter*, PSB and KMB of oven-dry soil was calculated by multiplying the average count per plate by the dilution factor and dividing by the oven-dry weight of one gram soil sample by the following formula:

population of 23.33 and 14.67 x 10⁵ cfu g⁻¹ soil at 50 per cent flowering and at harvest respectively. While, minimum KMB population was noticed in farmer's practice treatment (T₁).

Parallel results were recorded by Gorde *et al.* (2022) who noted a greater population of fungi detected with application of 100 % RDN through FYM, vermicompost, neem cake in treatment. The main cause of higher fungi population is dead food material present in vermicompost and FYM. Research by Korat and Mathukia (2022) suggests that the use of biofertilizers, vermicompost and farmyard manure (FYM) in organic farming practices leads to an increase in the number of bacteria in the soil. Similarly, Manna and Ganguly (2001) found that experimental modules enriched with substantial amounts of organic manure exhibited increased microbial populations. This suggests that organic matter serves as a vital food source for microbes, thereby enhancing their growth. Similar findings were observed by Bhatt *et al.* (2016) who noticed that application of 100 % NPK + 15 t FYM ha⁻¹ recorded higher population of actinomycetes after rice and wheat crops, respectively. Also, Rankov *et al.* (1981) reported positive effect of combined application of NPK fertilizers on microbial development and biological activity of the soil. Comparable outcomes were noted by Sheoran *et al.* (2018). In comparison to conventional farming system overall, population of *Azotobacter* increased significantly because of organic nutrient sources which showed a stimulating influence on the microbial populations of organic farming. Similar results were observed by Sharma *et al.* (2023) who found that the treatment T₃ *i.e.*, seed inoculation with MPKV consortium + 75 % RDF was found to have significantly higher population of KMB, *Azotobacter* at flowering stage (13.38 x 10⁵ cfu g⁻¹ of soil).

Effect of different farming practices on enzyme activity in soil at 50 per cent flowering and at harvest of wheat crop.

The observation for alkaline phosphatase enzyme activity in soil at 50 per cent flowering (12.32 µg PNP g⁻¹ hr⁻¹) and at harvest (11.07 µg PNP g⁻¹ hr⁻¹) recorded higher in organic farming treatment (T₃). Farmer's practice treatment (T₁) had lowest alkaline phosphatase activity in soil. The significantly higher acid phosphatase activity in soil at 50 per cent flowering (10.00 µg PNP g⁻¹ hr⁻¹) and at harvest (9.62

$\mu\text{g PNP g}^{-1} \text{hr}^{-1}$) were observed in organic farming treatment (T_3). Farmer's practice treatment (T_1) had minimum acid phosphatase activity in soil. Treatment T_3 i.e., organic farming recorded maximum urease activity in soil ($26.75 \mu\text{g NH}_4^+\text{-N g}^{-1} \text{hr}^{-1}$) at 50 per cent flowering and ($25.77 \mu\text{g NH}_4^+\text{-N g}^{-1} \text{hr}^{-1}$) at harvest. While least urease activity was recorded in farmer's practice treatment (T_1). The higher dehydrogenase activity ($14.12 \mu\text{g TPF g}^{-1} \text{soil } 24 \text{hr}^{-1}$) at 50 per cent flowering and ($13.70 \mu\text{g TPF g}^{-1} \text{soil } 24 \text{hr}^{-1}$) at harvest were recorded in organic farming treatment (T_3). Followed by climate resilient farming treatment and MPKV recommended package of practices treatment. Farmer's practice treatment (T_1) recorded lowest dehydrogenase activity (Table 2)

Nath and Yadav (2011) reported that application of FYM, coir pith waste, pressmud, digested sludge and poultry manure showed higher activity of alkaline phosphatase and dehydrogenase enzyme. Resembling outcomes were documented by Gorde *et al.* (2022) higher acid phosphatase enzyme activity was observed with application of organic matter in treatment. Okur *et al.* (2008) found that urease activity was notably greater in organic farming systems compared to conventional ones. Similarly, Melero *et al.* (2006) observed that soils managed organically exhibited higher urease activity than those managed with inorganic methods. Singh *et al.* (2007) also stated that incorporation of organic matter in the soil increased dehydrogenase activity in the soil.

Effect of farming practices on yield of wheat

The results depicts that the climate resilient farming showed higher yield of grain (T_5) i.e., 43.16 q ha^{-1} and yield of straw i.e., 59.56 q ha^{-1} . The MPKV recommended package of practices (T_2) yielded impressive results, achieving grain and straw outputs of $41.72 \text{ q per ha}^{-1}$ and $55.90 \text{ q per ha}^{-1}$, respectively. Suggesting that recommended agricultural practices can significantly boost yield compared to traditional methods. Farmer's practice (T_1) showed grain yield of 35.05 q ha^{-1} . Organic farming (T_3) and Natural farming (T_4) showed lower grain yield of 26.58 q ha^{-1} and 20.10 q ha^{-1} respectively. Similarly, organic farming and natural farming showed lower yield of straw 34.82 q ha^{-1} and 26.74 q ha^{-1} , respectively (Table 3).

It has been concluded that under experimental and field conditions, yields (per hectare) from organic farming may reduce up to 20-25 % and 50 %, respectively, in comparison with conventional farming (Seufert and Ramankutty, 2017). Rasul and Thapa (2004) also reported that the yield gap between organic and conventional farming is a significant point of discussion. On average, organic farming yields tend to be lower by about 20-25 % compared to conventional methods.

Conclusion

The findings demonstrate that organic farming practices significantly enhance microbial populations and enzymatic activities in soil compared to conventional farming methods. It could be concluded that adopting organic farming can improve soil health and fertility, promoting better growth of the crop and sustainability in agricultural practices. The lower yields observed in organic farming during the first year can be attributed to several factors, including soil health, nutrient availability and the time required for organic methods to become fully effective. As the soil ecosystem develops over time, there is potential for significant yield improvements. These findings were based on field experiment conducted over a single season with the wheat crop, it is recommended to continue the experiment further in subsequent years is essential to assess the effects of different agricultural methods on both soil quality and yield of wheat crop.

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Table 1. Effect of different farming practices on microbial population in soil at 50 per cent flowering and at harvest of wheat crop

Treat No.	Farming practices	Fungal population (x 10 ⁵ cfu g ⁻¹ soil)		Bacterial population (x 10 ⁶ cfu g ⁻¹ soil)		Actinomycetes population (x 10 ⁴ cfu g ⁻¹ soil)		<i>Azotobacter</i> (x 10 ⁵ cfu g ⁻¹ soil)		PSB population (x 10 ⁵ cfu g ⁻¹ soil)		KMB population (x 10 ⁵ cfu g ⁻¹ soil)	
		50% flowering	At harvest	50% flowering	At harvest	50% flowering	At harvest	50% flowering	At harvest	50% flowering	At harvest	50% flowering	At harvest
T ₁	Farmer's practice	19.42	13.83	191.92	184.83	30.33	24.67	21.08	17.58	20.33	12.17	14.58	9.75
T ₂	MPKV recommended package of practices	21.83	16.58	212.25	204.67	33.67	29.42	26.67	21.17	24.17	17.08	21.92	13.08
T ₃	Organic farming	24.17	17.42	214.17	208.92	35.42	30.08	29.42	22.92	25.67	19.25	23.33	14.67
T ₄	Natural farming	19.67	14.00	193.08	186.25	31.83	25.58	21.75	17.75	21.08	13.42	17.08	10.33
T ₅	Climate resilient farming	24.25	17.17	210.25	207.50	33.75	30.17	27.92	21.83	25.08	18.33	22.17	13.42
S.E(m) ±		1.00	0.59	2.75	3.03	1.01	0.59	1.08	0.86	1.00	0.69	0.85	0.56
C.D. @ 5%		3.08	1.83	8.47	9.33	3.11	1.81	3.31	2.64	3.10	2.11	2.62	1.73
Initial		13.67		183.75		14.50		17.33		12.67		10.12	

Effect of different farming practices on enzyme activity in soil at 50 per cent flowering and at harvest of wheat crop

Tr. No.	Farming practices	Alkaline phosphatase enzyme (µg PNP g ⁻¹ hr ⁻¹)		Acid phosphatase enzyme (µg PNP g ⁻¹ hr ⁻¹)		Urease enzyme (µg NH ₄ ⁺ -N g ⁻¹ hr ⁻¹)		Dehydrogenase enzyme (µg TPF g ⁻¹ soil 24 hr ⁻¹)	
		50% flowering	At harvest	50% flowering	At harvest	50% flowering	At harvest	50% flowering	At harvest
T ₁	Farmer's practice	8.12	7.56	6.20	5.96	21.90	19.10	11.49	10.23
T ₂	MPKV recommended package of practices	10.82	9.74	9.06	8.66	25.90	24.67	13.63	11.98
T ₃	Organic farming	12.32	11.07	10.00	9.62	26.75	25.77	14.12	13.70
T ₄	Natural farming	9.91	9.16	6.39	6.06	22.70	19.67	11.85	10.99
T ₅	Climate resilient farming	11.88	10.68	9.22	8.84	26.70	25.60	13.72	12.85
S.E(m) ±		0.52	0.49	0.33	0.33	0.89	3.22	0.62	0.58
C.D. @ 5%		1.63	1.51	1.03	1.03	2.78	1.03	1.95	1.79
Initial		9.12	-	6.10	-	19.87	-	10.08	-

Table 3. Effect of farming practices on yield of wheat

Tr. No.	Treatments	Grain (q ha ⁻¹)	Straw (q ha ⁻¹)
T ₁	Farmer's practice	35.05	45.21
T ₂	MPKV recommended package of practices	41.72	55.90
T ₃	Organic farming	26.58	34.82
T ₄	Natural farming	20.10	26.74
T ₅	Climate resilient farming	43.16	59.56
S. E(m) ±		1.36	1.80
C.D. @ 5%		4.25	5.61